

LINGUOCULTUROLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF ANTHROPNYMIC COMPONENT STABLE COMPOUNDS IN LITERARY

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Abstract: this article defines that Linguoculturological properties of anthroponymic component stable compounds in literary. Moreover there was given different effective researchers in it.

Key words: interpretation, national-esthetic worldview, ethno-cultural concepts, epoch attributes, historical exoticism, ethnographical accuracy, national identity

It is obscure to know the local culture which uses the same language for their communication. Besides, the native language they use represents spiritual life of people. It is should be mentioned that A. Kaydarov, who is a scientist and academician said: «A language is the basis of not only communication between people, but also the symbol of culture and spiritual world of those people. The language is unique to present the local culture, the reason of existence, viewpoint and the way of living. Thus, languages play an important role in delivering the national heritage from generation to generation» [1]. Therefore, the history and culture of the nation, the way of living and their spiritual world are especially represented in the names of people. Because, we may the thoughts and intentions of the people according to the people's names. The linguistic branch which investigates the names of people is called onomastics or name-study.

Onomastics – basically, is the study of common names, but it includes proper names. It was a specific sub-branch which studies proper names.

There are some sub-branches of onomastics in linguistics such as anthroponyms, toponyms, cosmonomy, astronomy, zoo names, phytonomy ethno names. Therefore, there have been researched on ethimological study methods and ways of using anthroponyms in different resources from different points of view.

Every branch of the onomastics is straightly connected with the linguistics, therefore, their study methods and strategies are based on the general methods of linguistics. Hence, the methods and strategies which are used in linguistics for the study of lexicology are also applied in the study of onomastic etymology. In fact, the methods used in linguistics can be used in the research on onomastics. They are: 1) descriptive (сипаттама), historical-comparative, (компаративтік) historical-comparative (typological), phonetic, morphological.

However, the methods which are used in onomastics can be in different directions to study. Because, the analysis of onimastics can be of various types. There

are a number of analysis of onomastics such as etymological, derivative, formative, stylistic, differential- genetic etc.

Anthroponymics – is a branch of onomastics which studies the names of people, proper names, patronyms (the names of father), surnames, nicknames, pseudonyms, cryptonyms. «Names – memory of each period, the historical chain continued from generation to generation, the historical mirror for the national identity» [2]. In this respect, the investigation of proper names is important for not only history but also “*Uzbek translatology*”.

The linguistic aspect of anthroponyms refers to defining national consciousness, especially, anthroponym is not studied from linguistic point of view but also accorfn to its history, background and the sphere of its use. This is investigated as a source of information which gives the local tradition, customs and the social life. In general, the theoretical basis was studied by Russian linguist-scientists such as V.D. Bondaletov, N.A. Baskakov, S.I. Zinin, Yu. A. Karpenko, A.A. Refornatskiy, M.A. Selishev, O.N. Trubachev, N.N. Tupikov, V.P. Moroshkin, A.V. Superanskaya, etc. Besides, there are a lot of Uzbek scientists who wrote significant works about the study of onomastics. The first person to mention is a professor T. Januzakov. After that, we can name such scientists as A. Kaydar, B.M. Tilewberdiev, Z.K. Akhmetjanova, U.A. Musabekova. It is important to point out several linguists such as M.D. Musabaeva and G. Madieva. 10

T. Januzakov investigated proper names in Uzbek in a complete system. He revealed the ways of development of Uzbek anthroponyms, systematized the grammatical and semantic description of names. He created a system concerning its basis and developed a dictionary of proper names. There are a number of works related to Uzbek anthroponyms and onomastics by the author and one of them is called “History of Uzbek names” («Қазақ есімдерінің тарихы») (1971). Besides, there is a distionary called “Uzbek names” («Қазақ есімдері») (1988) developed together by K. Esbaeva and T. Januzakov, a manual “Mystery of names” («Есімдер сыры») (2004), “Uzbek onomastics: achievements and its future” («Қазақ ономастикасы: жетістіктері мен болашағы») (2004), “Uzbek onomastics” («Қазақ ономастикасы – Казахская ономастика») 1 Volume (2006) etc. T. Januzakov made an analytical analysis of great importance in his work called “Uzbek onomastics” relating to the history of onomastics. The study of anthroponyms, the history of Uzbek anthroponyms, types of Uzbek anthroponyms, derivative ways, people’s names, patriotic names and surnames and their issues of writing have been deeply investigated in above mentioned works. In addition, there have been discussed the semantic and functional aspects of nicknames, tabu and folk names, the relation of ethnic names with anthroponyms, the connection of anthroponyms with toponyms as well. Accordingly, T. Januzakov divided the Uzbek names into lexical-semantic

groups in accordance with their derivative aspect[2]: 1) names related to farming: Bota, Buka, Akkozy, Kulinshak, Jilqibay, etc. 2) names related to natural phenomenon: Taubay, Boran, Kunay, Ayday, Sholpan etc. 3) names related to hunting, animals and birds: Arystan, Tulkibay, Burkit, Qarligash, Lashin etc. 4) names related to metals and precious things like: Altyn, Bolat, Gauhar, Marjan, Jibek, Torgyn etc. 5) names related to plants: Qyzgaldaq, Rayxan, Guljan etc. 6) names related to vegetables and fruits: Alma, Anar, Meyiz, Jangaq, Sarymsaq etc. 7) names related to relationship cases: Atabek, Baba, Dadabay, Jienbay etc. 8) names related to land and water: Altay, Alatau, Aralbay, Oral, Edil, Ertis etc. 9) names related to housing furniture and other properties: Ayranbay, Suttibay, Shirinbay, Sheker etc. However, the system of naming in English is based on lining 4 names altogether, so there are only four names one after another like: *Charles Philip Arthur George, Andrew Albert Christian Edward, Edward Antony Richard Louise, Anne Elithabeth Alice Louise*. This is defined in the *The Oxford Companion to English Literature* in such a way: First name is *Christian name* («Бірінші есімі») – this is the name given to a person when he is born, middle name (*second-middle name*) – is the name of characteristics, in addition to this, there is a *maiden name*, then, it is accepted to add concerning fathers' names or close relatives' names as well, the last name is called *surname or last name*. In general, the most historical event which affected the English to have such changes in the English language was the Normand conquered of England. In 1066, the Normads county whose name was Wilhelm took reign over Anglo-Saxon land. After the conquer, worker who spoke Normand and French ran the work of most civil and church labor, then, they brought their own names denying Anglo-Saxon names. We can make a conclusion that this influenced to English anthroponyms, first of all, in terms of the local culture, history and development. Therefore, anthroponyms as T. Januzakov noticed [2]: «Although people's names and their surnames with background names are known to human being, their meaning is not always clear to everybody. Because, some of them relates to old history, so the meanings of such names are indefinite». For instance, among Uzbek anthroponyms there are such names as Barlibay (-ev, -eva), Qaratay (-ev, -eva), Abaq (-ov, -ova), etc. which is difficult to translate them into another language as their etymology is unclear to the translator himself.

Translation – not a profession, – art. It can be effective if we dedicate to the art our whole life. Therefore, equivalent translation is not used for the translation of anthroponyms like we use in other translation. If the translator could find the key words to the any statement, it can be far from its original. Because, the translation of anthroponyms differs from other types of translation. The Uzbek names may be different according to their structure and etymology. Because, they belong to earlier

centuries and mid-centuries, mid-centuries and late centuries. So, it is obvious to have a historic effect in their meaning.

All in all, proper names, especially, toponyms, anthroponyms, ethnic names, cosmonyms have a special focus to investigate them in accordance with their etymology. So, they need to be studied accordingly. According to the point of T. Januzakov, such kind of feature – the common names and proper names have lexical-semantic dichotomy, more precisely, to translate them depends on the word of lexical meaning and lexical meaningless words.

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